

CHAPTER 1

MODERN TRENDS IN PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION

PANIC AS A FACTOR OF INFORMATION SECURITY THREAT

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Abstract. Security has always been the most important goal and fundamental need of both the individual and society as a whole, as the formation and development of human society has always been associated with overcoming of various threats posed by nature, enemies, technical facilities and others. Information risks involve, first of all, a form of negative impact on the individual, society and the state as a whole, using all types of information. In this case, a direct impact on the mind and consciousness of people is carried out to form the necessary thoughts and judgments, which then in some way guide the people behavior. Ensuring national security is the most important condition for the functioning and development of human society, which requires consideration of socio-political, economic, legal, geopolitical, environmental, man-made and a number of other aspects. Among the various components, information security of national security plays a special role.

In this article it is considered the concept of panic, its impact on information security of the state and society, information factors as the main causes of panic and methods of combating it. Among the preconditions for panic there are mentioned psychological, physiological, socio-psychological factors, the sudden appearance and accumulation of negative information content. The most effective means of struggle against panic are persuasion, categorical order, explanation of the danger fallacy, use of force, elimination (isolation) of the most dangerous alarmists.

It has been proved that the prevention of panic in society, chaos in the system of state regulation depends on high-quality national information security, which consists of regulating the information space and conducting a competent state information policy.

Keywords: state, society, political conflicts, hybrid war, information, rumors, panic, fear, panic disorder, stress resistance.

JEL classification: H12, H55, H56

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Introduction. The new and recent history of Europe and Ukraine presents a lot of examples of panic reactions, usually accompanied by various social cataclysms and shocks of global (World War I and World War II, revolutions) and local scale (forms of social protest, terrorist actions, military conflicts in Georgia and Ukraine). Most of these actions were accompanied by extreme intolerance, exacerbation of passions and, as a consequence, the appearance of psychopathic and panic symptoms.

Society is able to feel fear, apprehension, irritation, anger and others that cause motivated and unmotivated impulses, aggression, and panic on the part of society or individual components of its groups. This is especially true in times of information wars and psychological pressure on society. Hence the need to study the patterns of

panic behavior at people under conditions of information chaos and cognitive dissonance.

Literature Review. The phenomenon of panic has complex character for research, which is due to the suddenness of its occurrence, as well as the difficulty in such a situation to remain an observer, because anyone who is "inside" the panic system, to some extent exposed to it. Therefore, existing studies of this phenomenon remain at the level of descriptions made after its peak. Despite the complexity of studying this problem, the phenomenon of panic attracts the attention of domestic and foreign experts, among them are H. Andreeva [1], V. Androssiuk [6], I. Havrilets [2], V. Krysko [3], A. Nazaretyan [4], D. Olshansky [5], V. Semikov [7], A. Sliusar [8], Jürgen Margraf [9], Hans Morschitzky [10] and others. In their researches, they were able to identify the main characteristics of the phenomenon, the peculiarities of its occurrence, and the most importantly - the possible mechanisms of working with it in various emergencies, but the phenomenon of panic within the information space and its impact on national security has not been studied.

Aims. Identification of the preconditions for panic and investigation of its impact on information security of the state and society.

Methods. The author used the methods of logical comparison, systematization and generalization, which made it possible to achieve the goal of the study.

Results. The role of information and information technologies in the modern world is extremely large. Information security is determined by the degree of protection and resilience of the main spheres of life in relation to dangerous, destabilizing, destructive, affecting the interests of the country information influences at the level of both implementation and retrieval of information.

Information security occupies a special place in the general system of national security of the state, as it is an element of all components of the latter, as a result of which it simultaneously acquires an autonomous meaning. Any challenges or threats to the country's national security are directly related to its information factor.

The current Ukrainian socio-economic situation, the imperfection of the state power organization and civil society create a wide range of internal threats to information security of the country, and therefore, the actual becomes the problem of creating and maintaining a secure environment for information exchange, which realizes the rules and policies of state security is because the information has lost the secondary role, becoming an important and impressive factor with its characteristics, due to the profit that can be obtained from its use. But there is a possibility of damage to the owner of the information by unauthorized penetration into the information structure and the impact on its components.

Information security, as a component of national security is the condition of vital interests of man, society and the state protection, when harm is prevented thanks to: incompleteness, untimeliness and unreliability of the used information; negative information impact; negative consequences of information technology use; unauthorized dissemination, use and violation of the integrity, confidentiality and availability of information.

In modern society, panic can be considered as one of the main factors threatening information security. Since, panic is a very dangerous psychological condition that requires decisive, including informational, actions to prevent the injection and spread. Panic behavior is typical for situations where people are deprived of help, support, torn from the usual way of life and do not know exactly what actions will be true.

The damage from panic often far exceeds the damage from the phenomenon that caused it (information and psychological wars, natural disasters, fires, bankruptcies, etc.). The consequences of the latter are negative phenomena of socio-social, socio-psychological, material, and even physical nature.

Panic is a special emotional state that occurs due to lack of information about some incomprehensible and frightening phenomenon, situations or, conversely, due to its excessive volume. It is manifested in the impulsive actions of individuals, groups of people or crowds. During this state, people are driven by a strong unconscious fear. They lose self-control, fuss, do not see any way out of the situation, and try to escape even at the cost of the death of others.

Etymologically, the term "panic" implies the mass nature of the phenomenon. In psychology, it is common to distinguish mass and individual panic. In addition, mass panic does not necessarily result in the form of a panic crowd. It can be expressed in a sense of doom and paralysis of the will, when the mass of people becomes incapable of decisive action in a critical situation, refuses to seek independent solutions.

Panic crowd is a subspecies of the current crowd (along with other subspecies: aggressive, selfish and insurgent one). Experience shows that this is the most dangerous of all types of crowds. In terms of the number of direct human casualties, mass panic usually far exceeds, for example, an aggressive crowd, but it is not inferior in long-term consequences.

The prevailing mood in society is also able, despite the extreme forms, to turn into a sharp deterioration of mental and physical health, economic downturn, a sharp decline in life expectancy, fertility and, consequently, - depopulation processes.

There are several prerequisites for the emergence and development of panic:

1. Physiological preconditions, such as fatigue, hunger, insomnia, depression, stress, drug intoxication, weaken people physically and mentally, reduce the ability to assess the situation quickly and accurately.

2. Psychological preconditions (feelings of pain, surprise, insecurity, fear and even more horror, feelings of isolation, helplessness) contribute to panic increase. These factors are regarded as natural activators of fear.

3. Socio-psychological preconditions (lack of group solidarity, integrity, group unity, loss of trust to the leadership, lack of information, panic rumors).

4. The sudden appearance of a threat to life, health, safety (for example, during a fire, explosion, accident, the rapid spread of emergency news, etc.).

5. Accumulation of so-called "psychological fuel" and, then, operation as a "relay", some or other mental catalyst. Prolonged feelings, fears, accumulation of anxiety, uncertainty of the situation, anticipated dangers and troubles - all this creates

a favorable background for panic, and the catalyst in this case can be any event. Not only strong fright, fear, but also some words, someone's behavior, some signals, even those that are not related to the expected dangers, can cause panic.

The main reasons of panic are mostly informational factors:

- Information and psychological unwillingness of people to adequately perceive what happened, the lack of specific information and, as a consequence, the presence of a kind of "information anarchy";
- The uniqueness of each extreme situation, which creates extreme tension in the event of a collision with it;
- Poor preparation of most people for rational action in case of danger;
- The presence in the crowd of emotionally unstable people who become in a critical situation as catalysts for negative rumors and panic as such.

The results of panic can be a significant deformation of assessments of what is happening, reduced readiness for adequate actions, increasing fear, increased susceptibility to external influences. And in a more pronounced form, this condition can lead to complete insanity and loss of control over their behavior. A person can run away, having no purpose for it, to rush senselessly, to perform unmotivated, chaotic actions and deeds.

Panic states are very often caused by neurotic fears, i.e. those that are inadequate to the objective danger and are rather signs of internal distress. This fact is so characteristic that some authors define panic as: "horror caused by imaginary danger".

Fear, as many psychologists point out, is a reflection of the modern world in which humanity lives. A person is in a state of constant anxiety, fear lurks him/her everywhere. A person who is strongly influenced by fear often loses control of him, does not take self-defense measures, bad orients in the situation and may give in to panic if the fear turns into stress.

Fear for some time can be considered physiologically normal and even useful, because it contributes to the emergency mobilization of physical and mental stress, which is necessary for self-preservation. It acts as a protective mechanism that saves humanity from premature death. There are no "fearless" mentally normal people. If a person does not respond to danger, it is an indicator of the development of mental pathology. Thus, fear is a normal defensive reaction to abnormal, extraordinary circumstances.

In particular, the phenomenon of panic and its consequences can be traced during the information-psychological war, which is considered a special kind of relationship between the subjects, in which methods and means of informational influence on the mental state and activities of people are used to resolve contradictions. The result of the latter is tension, anxiety and fear.

Destructive factors of hybrid (information-psychological) war that do not stop can cause lasting changes in people with low levels of stress, thereby weakening the human resources of the state and the national security system in general.

Very often rumors become a special form of mass exchange of unreliable or distorted oral information and a phenomenon that opposes security protection.

Rumors usually arise in the absence of complete and reliable information on the current problem for people. Information transmitted in the form of rumors occurs, as a rule, spontaneously and has an unauthorized, uncontrolled and uncontrolled nature. A necessary and sufficient condition for the emergence of rumors is often the presence of unmet actual needs of people or threats to the safety of their lives.

Under these situations, even the most incredible messages transmitted informally, as if "in secret", can arouse interest and become widespread in the form of rumors. Thus, the main reason for the emergence and spread of the latter in society is the dissatisfaction of people's information needs, a kind of "information collapse" or vice versa "information chaos", especially in emergent real-life situations.

At the state level, the appearance of rumors is characterized by insufficient efficiency and objectivity of information, its political bias, excessive closeness (secrecy), and the desire to smooth out in the course of informing the public the severity of what is happening. It is in response to such actions rumors begin to present the situation in an exaggeratedly dramatic way. They are always an emotionally compensatory result of insufficiently complete or biased information provided by official services

One of the tasks of the state information security is to prevent the presence of rumors, and in case of their occurrence is to prevent panic. Therefore, the state policy of information security is an important component of national security. It should be based on systematic preventive activities of public administration bodies to provide information security guarantees to individuals, social groups, society and the state as a whole.

Discussion. Information provision of the national security plays an important multifaceted role in determining national interests and national security priorities. To ensure the information security of the state it is necessary to fully meet the needs of citizens, enterprises, institutions and organizations of all forms of ownership in access to reliable and objective information; preservation and increase of spiritual, cultural and moral values of the Ukrainian people; development of media culture of society and socially responsible media environment; formation of an effective legal system to protect the individual, society and the state from destructive propaganda influences; creation on the basis of norms of the international law of system and mechanisms of protection against negative external information and psychological influences, first of all, propaganda; development of cultural information society.

Conclusions. Panic is understood as one of the types of the crowd behavior, which are in conditions of behavioral uncertainty in increased emotional arousal from an uncontrollable feeling of fear. Panic has contagious feature, which can affect a large number of people and deprive them of common sense. Both extreme situations (fire, fight) and the spread of unfounded rumors in the information space can lead to panic. Counteracting panic is extremely difficult and the most effective means of fighting against panic are: persuasion, categorical order, explanation of danger falsity, use of force, elimination (isolation) of the most dangerous fear mongers. To counteract the spread of rumors, information must be: operational, i.e. timely communicated to the population; open and credible, because creating a

misconception about the risks, concealment or denial of the facts, their omission will bring only harm; clear, i.e. should be provided so that it is understood by the target audience (however, this should not harm the actual accuracy or completeness of the information); continuous, because if the information is not updated regularly, it is forgotten; objective and timely.

Ensuring information security was and remains one of the most actual and significant issues of today. Security and completeness of information, filling the information space with reliable information, ensuring the realization of citizens' rights to access information - all this affects the preservation of the integrity and independence of the state.

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